

ISSUES OF USING THE EXPERIENCES OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CATERING ENTERPRISES OF OUR REPUBLIC

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***Annotation:** In this article, the main attention given to the issues of researching the experience gained in the market of catering services of foreign countries and developing the working performance of catering enterprises of our Republic.*

***Key words:** service industry, services market, catering company, restaurant, service, cafe, bar, digital technologies, artificial intelligence, innovation, electronic menu.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, in the conditions of globalization that is occurring in the world economy, market relations are deepening, and the importance of innovative approaches and digital technologies in the economy is increasing. In such conditions, the share of the service sector in the global GDP has averaged 60 %¹ in the last ten years, and it has become a “driver” sector among the sectors of the world economy, which indicates the rapid adaptability of this sector to the trends observed in the world economy.

In our country, after we gained independence, a number of constructive works are being carried out to build and develop our economy based on market laws. As a

¹<https://www.statista.com/statistics/256563/share-of-economic-sectors-in-the-global-gross-domestic-product/>

result of these large-scale socio-economic reforms, growth dynamics are observed in all branches and sectors of our national economy. In particular, we can cite the fact that the share of the service sector in the GDP of our country has been on average 40% for the last five years.

As a result of our transition to an economy based on market relations in our republic, positive changes were observed in the service sector as well as in a number of sectors and industries. In particular, the process of privatization has accelerated in the public catering network, which provides accommodation and catering services to the population, and catering enterprises of various ownership forms have begun to be established. Specifically, statistics show that in the last ten years, the number of economic entities providing accommodation and food services within the framework of enterprises and organizations operating in the sector of the economy of our republic has increased by 24,807 and made 36,811. we can see (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. The number of Enterprises Providing Catering Services in Uzbekistan.¹

¹Information from the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. www.state.uz

At the same time, it should be noted that the development of national catering Enterprises is formed by changes in consumer preferences, culinary trends and economic factors. Public catering businesses include a wide range of businesses providing services through food and beverages for events, institutions, businesses and individuals. Various factors, influence on the development of public serveries.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY.

Research on the issues of developing a national catering network, ensuring the effectiveness of services in the national catering services market and modernizing the works of public catering enterprises has been researched by a number of scientists from our country, such as J.Kurbanov¹, I.Tukhliyev², T.Sharipov³, D.Aslanova⁴, I.Erbotayev⁵, Sh.Saifuddinov⁶, S.Safaeva⁷, I.Ivatov⁸ and others. In Particular, J.Kurbanov and R.Kurbanova In their research work, gurbanova has carried out research on the issues of modernization of public catering enterprises and improving the efficiency of service in them, and made scientific proposals for the development of the activities of catering enterprises.

D.Aslanova, T.Khudayshukurov, and N.Mominov in the educational manual “Dunyo xalqlari ovqatlanishining o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari (*Peculiarities of the People’s Nutrition Whole Around the World*)”, touched on the economic improvement of catering enterprises in our country and the factors affecting works of catering enterprises.

¹J.Kurbanov, R.Kurbanova. “Umumiy ovqatlanish korxonalarini modernizatsiyalash va ularda xizmatlar ko‘rsatish samaradorligini oshirish”. Monograph. – 2020., J.Kurbanov, R.Kurbanova. “Xizmat ko‘rsatish korxonalarining elektron texnikasi”. – Samarkand, 2017. - 169 p.

²I.Tukhliyev, R.Hayitboyev, B.Sh.Safarov, G.R.Tursunova. “Turizm”, Textbook, - T., 2014. - 389 p

³T.S.Sharipov. “Umumiy ovqatlanish korxonalarini samaradorligini oshirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish (Samarqand viloyati misolida)”. Dissertation abstract for the degree of candidate of economic sciences. - S.: SamISI, 2010.

⁴D.Aslanova, T.Xudayshukurov, N.Mominov. “Dunyo xalqlari ovqatlanishining o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari”. Study guide. - T., 2006. - 7 p.

⁵I.Erbotayev. Umumiy ovqatlanish va xizmat madaniyati. Books I and II. Study guide. - T.: Abdulla Qodiriy nomidagi xalq merosi, 2003. – 3- 288 p.

⁶Sh.Saifuddinov, F.Xalimova. “Servis faoliyati” Study guide. – T.: Iqtisodiyot – 2019.

⁷S.Safaeva. Restoran biznesida zamonaviy marketing tadqiqotlarining o‘rni. // Birja-ekspert. №1. 2012, S.Safaeva Restoran biznesi marketingi. Study guide. - T.:TDIU, 2014. – 284 p.

⁸I.Ivatov. Restoran menejmenti. Study guide. - T.: Iqtisodiyot, 2007.

Sh.Saifuddinov and F.Khalimova expressed their opinion in their educational manual" service activities" about the role and importance of public catering enterprises in strengthening the flow of tourists to our country.

However, the issues related to the existing experiences and positive results of foreign countries achieved in this direction in the development of the market of catering services of our republic are not sufficiently researched.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

During today's rapid development, the market of catering services of foreign countries is rapidly developing through the transformation of technologies related to food processing, the development of communications, means of supply of products and raw materials, the activation of many production processes.

Currently, as a result of the formation and widespread popularity of the culture of human visits to catering enterprises and the growing demand for catering services in the world, the desire to organize work on the basis of modern approaches to the activities of catering services and enterprises providing these services is growing. These changes are associated with the emergence of new goals aimed at deepening the financial independence of enterprises, improving management methods and increasing competitiveness.

Trends in the catering sector of the United States, Japan and Western European countries indicate that investments in catering enterprises are among those that are fast-absorbing and have the opportunity to make a profit in the short term. Investments in the catering sector in these countries have an average turnover, and this happens 4-5 times faster than the average for all enterprises of the economy of these countries.

Common catering establishments in the catering services market of foreign countries today are as follows:

- cafeterias in the form of "check", such as kitchens and cafes (semi-automated and fully automated);

- fast food cafeterias
- grill bars;
- cafe “shop”;
- small restaurants and other businesses that work on the basis of the use of ready-made food or semi-finished products.

Today, almost all countries have been suffering from different cases associated with improper nutrition (overweight, increased blood pressure, diabetes mellitus, gout, etc.). However, in South Korea, this indicator is much lower, and for this reason, it is advisable to study the experiments related to nutrition in this state.

The food services market in the South Korean state is developing in connection with the growing infrastructure and transportation development, as well as the increased demand for fast food. The South Korean food service industry can be divided into full-service restaurants, fast-service restaurants, street shopping stalls and kiosks, cafes and bars, among others. The catering market in this country is divided into independent food service and chain catering service. The main participants in the above market are "Starbucks", " Yum! Brands", “McDonald’s”, “Balwoo Gongyang”, “Yongsusan”, "Burger King", etc. Catering services in South Korea can be defined as a service-oriented business in hospitals, homes, hotels, studios, remote locations, cruise ships, gardens, or venues for weddings, banquets, or events for major corporate meetings.¹

Currently, as a result of the development of digital technologies, the use of an artificial intelligence-based robotic system is gaining popularity in South Korean catering enterprises.

In fact, during today’s rapid development, it is not difficult to notice the influence of artificial intelligence on various aspects of our life. In particular, in the catering enterprises of developed countries of the world, the robotic system today suffers a lot, and the South Korean state is clear evidence of this. In the context of

¹<https://www.expermarketresearch.com/reports/south-korea-food-service-market>

South Korean cuisine, some robotic restaurants include automation in the preparation and serving of traditional Korean dishes, offering a futuristic twist to the dining experience. This may include robotic arms for cooking, automated conveyor systems for food delivery, and even robotic servers for bringing dishes to tables. One notable example is the use of robotic arms for tasks such as cooking meat in Korean barbecue restaurants. These sophisticated robotic systems can accurately cook and rotate meat, allowing precise control of the cooking process. In addition, some establishments use robots for tasks such as making noodles, making dumplings, and even serving customers, and this creates a unique and futuristic dining environment.

When the activities of many South Korean-based restaurants are studied, you can witness that robots, and not working waiters, accept orders from customers. In addition, special electronic menus inform consumers of the energy value (kcal) contained in any dish. This creates additional comfort for the end-users in their bakery. Below we can see, as an example, robots designed for use in recently created catering enterprises of companies in the South Korean state, which create similar artificial intelligence. Today, South Korea's Knowledge Transfer (KT) company has launched two new service robots, both based on artificial intelligence (AI) technology, aimed at restaurants seeking to ease their operational burdens using robots. Two new generations of service robots based on artificial intelligence are designed to transport food and drink in a variety of indoor environments, including uneven tiles and uneven surfaces, using suspension construction devices optimized for stability. In addition, stability is significantly improving, so now several robots can work in one place at the same time. Another feature of the new robots is that they are adapted to work in coordination with kiosks or tablets in catering establishments and stores. For example, robots will respond to customers if they have a request or call from a tablet on the table.

The development of today's digital technologies has a significant impact on enterprises operating in the catering sector, among the sectors of the economy. Online platforms and mobile apps have made it easier for consumers to find and engage in

catering services while allowing catering businesses to simplify their activities and expand their customer base. In addition, the technology has facilitated the use of data analysis and customer relationship management systems, allowing catering businesses to better understand their customers' wishes and adapt their services accordingly. There are many convenient aspects of using artificial intelligence (robots) in catering enterprises, the main of which are: to prevent labor shortages, reduce excessive time spent in the process of activity, increase profits in exchange for a reduction in the salary paid to workers, ensure the accuracy and transparency of the services provided at the enterprise.

CONCLUSION

As we all know, catering establishments play an important role in the food industry by providing services through a wide range of foods and beverages for various activities. As consumer demand for catering services grows, businesses need to adapt to changing consumer preferences, dietary restrictions, and culinary trends. The application of sustainability practices, the offer of various menu options and excellent customer service are the main factors that distinguish catering establishments in a competitive market. In general, catering establishments provide a valuable service that brings people together through unforgettable eating experiences, making an important contribution to the culinary landscape.

We are now witnessing the rapid development of 21st century technologies. Catering establishments in developed countries of the world are also making good use of modern technical and technological innovations, and this provides them with great facilities. The international pandemic (COVID-19), which occurred in particular, meant how much modern technology is needed in catering enterprises. The COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated changes in the catering industry. In terms of safety and hygiene, contactless delivery as well as individual packaging spurred the transition. Remote work and virtual events also provided new opportunities for catering businesses to provide customized services to online meetings, conferences and virtual meetings. Catering establishments were also forced to adapt to emerging

food safety standards. The demand for creative and unique culinary experience has led catering businesses to invest in research and development to differentiate their offerings and stay ahead of industry trends. In addition, the globalization of catering culture has had a significant impact on the development of catering enterprises.

In general, the development of catering Enterprises is a dynamic process that continues to be formed by changing consumer behavior, culinary trends, technological advances and market dynamics. As the industry continues to develop, catering businesses will have to adapt to new challenges and opportunities, including digital transformation, sustainability, and the demands of emerging consumers, to succeed in a rapidly changing business environment.

We also want to develop catering enterprises in our country and increase the visit of residents and tourists to these enterprises through this, it is necessary that we comply with the above requirements and boldly introduce modern technologies and creative and modern innovative approaches in catering enterprises, and establish a more productive usefulness of existing resources in enterprises.

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